

Teaching Performance as Influenced by Satisfaction and Perspective towards Job

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Abstract:- The study aimed to determine the level of job satisfaction and perspective towards job and teaching performance among the faculty members. The research was carried out at San Agustin Institute of Technology in Valencia City, Bukidnon and was responded by 60 full-time regular and full-time probationary teachers during Second Semester S.Y. 2017-2018. To determine the associations between the variables in the study, the researcher employed a descriptive-correlational research design. The researcher adopted Satisfaction and Perspective towards Job Questionnaire (SPJQ) as primary data. Teachers Performance Evaluation data from the guidance office was gathered to serve as the secondary data to complete the study. The findings showed that faculty members are content with their jobs in terms of administrative support, salary, and interpersonal relationships; personal and organizational perspectives are both positive, and teachers have extremely satisfying teaching performance. Finally, job satisfaction and perspective towards job are not significant to teachers' teaching performance. Teachers perform satisfactorily because they have the pleasurable attitude towards their job and plain lifestyle which are critical elements for their success in their teaching endeavor.

Keywords:- Satisfaction, teaching performance, teaching perspective

I. INTRODUCTION

Teachers are assets of every educational institution and to become a highly competitive school, one must possess quality teachers. Well experienced, efficient, and competitive teachers put an edge of an institution. They help educate students to gain knowledge and molding them to become better and productive Filipino citizens. As a result, the performance of teachers is critical to the progress of the school and its students.

Employee's performance is one of the most essential aspect in most organizations. In Philippine educational institutions, performance is utilized to determine how the individual employee contributes to accomplishing its purpose and goals. Employees may raise their productivity, morale, and motivation as a result of feedback from these evaluation results (Galeon, 2015).

In this highly competitive society of today's generation, every educational institution must need productive teachers in order to fulfill their objectives and effectively respond to the needs of the students in terms of imparting knowledge and skills required for their growth

and success. Performance is one of the significant and primary needs for future career development and the success of institutions. High performance in personal obligations can be a source of happiness; thus, bad performance may be perceived as dissatisfying or even as an individual catastrophe. Besides, the way teachers perceive their job is also one of the substantial aspects to consider in evaluating work performance.

The Philippine education system is currently dealing with a number of problems, including ASEAN integration, Outcome-Based Education, and K12 Basic Education. Teachers will no longer be preoccupied solely with teaching duties, but also with other obligations. According to Vigoda, as cited by Miranda (2004), executed work performance refers to an individual's tasks and responsibilities as part of their work assignments; hence, failing to accomplish these responsibilities may result in a loss to the school. Moreover, if the teacher's performance is ineffective, this would lead to affecting the overall mission and vision of the school, particularly the process of delivering quality education to the students.

Fundamental issues that instructors encounter, as noted, include addressing student needs and poor public impression. In school, teachers must deal with a diverse spectrum of student necessities. where teaching makes it more a challenging career facing diverse students with varying backgrounds, needs, and learning styles. Additionally, the stigma is attached to teachers in private schools remain regarded "lower paid" as compared to the public school which pulls attention away from their high morale as teachers. Addressing these challenges and raising knowledge about the educational environment that teachers encounter on a daily basis can assist increase teacher retention, student success rates, and the overall quality of education in the school.

Thus, to fill the gaps in existing findings in the study regarding faculty members' satisfaction with work, perspectives, and teaching performance, the researcher strongly proposed this study to determine faculty members' job satisfaction and perspectives, as well as their influence on teaching performance.

II. METHODOLOGY

A quantitative approach using A descriptive-correlational study approach was employed to collect information on job satisfaction and respondents' attitudes toward their jobs. The study was conducted within June to July 2018 at Valencia City, Bukidnon, San Agustin Institute of Technology using faculty members during second

semester S.Y. 2017-2018 as respondents of this study. The researcher employed universal sampling which included all full-time regular and full-time probationary faculty members who taught for at least one (1) year in the institution during the second semester of the 2017-2018 academic year, with 42 full-time regular faculty members and 18 full-time probationary faculty members serving as respondents.

Satisfaction, Perspective towards Job, Questionnaire (SPJQ) were used as the primary data which covers the independent variables of the study, consisting of 45 indicators that are rated on 4 points Likert scale option and the teachers' performance evaluated by the students and principals or dean done during second semester S.Y. 2017-2018 served as the secondary data to complete the study. Moreover, the researcher conducted the study by distributing personally the questionnaire to the faculty members and had asked permission from the guidance office to obtain the secondary data (teachers' performance evaluation) to complete the study.

A descriptive method such as 1) frequency count to determine the responders' demographic profile to answer first set of questionnaires; 2) utilizing mean and standard deviation (SD) to ascertain the respondent's job satisfaction, job perspective, and teaching performance. Moreover, 3) Pearson product moment correlation was utilized to establish the significant association between respondents' teaching performance and job satisfaction, job viewpoint, and job perspective.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results revealed that there are 28 (46.67%) faculty members between the ages of 20 and 29 while there are 12 (20%) of them whose age ranges from 40-49 years old and finally, there were 11 (18%) who belonged to the 30 to 39 years of age. The least age group is 50 years and above with 9 (15%) of the teachers' counterpart. Teachers within the age range of 20-29 are usually newly hired teachers because of the considerable number of teachers' turnover at the end of the school year. Additionally, those who are in this age bracket still earn years of experience as an additional qualification when they feel moving out of the institution for greener pasture like grabbing opportunities in the public schools. Teachers within the 30-49 age group is career-focused, and most are teachers who are actively active in school activities and are very motivated to advance their professional growth and development. Further, they are after what they accomplished for they have still the high desire to get the promotion. They work hard to earn money because they understand the value of labor as a means of subsistence. For individuals above the age of 50, usually teachers of this age bracket, already find fulfillment in their respective designation and workplaces. In terms of the teaching-learning process, these teachers are already competent in the delivery of the lesson. Kersaint, Lewis, Potter, and Meisels (2007) did study that incorporates educators' active participation and appreciation for the importance of work. Teachers who have been seriously impacted prefer to stay in the classroom until they are between the ages of 30 and 50.

Table 1: The Demographic Characteristics of Faculty Members of San Agustin Institute of Technology

Age	f	%
20-29 years old	28	46.67
30-39 years old	11	18.33
40-49-years old	12	20.00
50 years above	9	15.00
Total	60	100.00
Gender	f	%
Male	19	31.67
Female	41	68.33
Total	60	100.00
Length of Service	f	%
1-3 years	30	50.00
4-8 years	8	13.33
9-13 years	7	11.67
14-18 years	5	8.33
19 years and above	10	16.67
Total	60	100.00
Educational Qualification	f	%
Associate Degree	0	0.00
Bachelor's Degree	42	70.00
Master's Degree	13	21.67
Doctorate Degree	5	8.33
Total	60	100.00

As to gender, majority of the faculty members are females with 41 or 68.33% while there were 19 or 31.67% of them belongs to male counterparts. It implies that female teachers occupy the teaching profession. According to Paton (2013), The early years of teaching are regarded as nurturing, and females are regarded as more nurturing than males because female teachers remain more patient and sensitive in handling pupil needs. Based on surveys conducted female teachers tend to be more precise in teaching their pupils based on motherly instinct. Female teachers usually are effective in classroom management because of the mother figure they portray in the class.

The study found that most of the faculty members served the school within 1-3 years of service composing of 50% in the over-all total of participants. It is followed by the faculty who rendered 19 years and above which consisting 16%. Faculty members who rendered 14-18 years got the lowest percentage (8.33%) of the total number of respondents. It implies that majority of faculty members just rendered their service in less than three years for them to earn experience for better opportunities and they tend to leave the institution after. That is why only a few faculty members with 4-8, 9-13 year and 14-18 years remain to serve to teach the institution. Considering that employees'

salary in school if almost half different than that of the public schools' counterpart, Salary and incentives are also important factors in deciding whether to stay or leave. Sabagh (2008) States that insufficient or low salaries are the possible reasons that pushes teachers to vacate their professions, according to (Towse, Kent, Osaki, & Kiruak, 2002; Kersaint et al., 2007).

Pertinent to educational qualification, the vast majority of responders are in their bachelor's degree with 42 or 70.00% while 13 or 21.67% and 5 or 8.33% held master's degrees and doctoral degrees respectively. It tells that most of the teachers are fresh graduates and working towards their professional development and advancement, that later,

they would have harvested the fruits of their labor for educational attainment is remunerated accordingly by the institution upon showing one's credentials. Buchanan et al. (2013), who investigated the factors, confirmed this finding influencing instructors' choices to stay or leave the career. They found that teachers remain at school longer than the others once They liked the opportunity for professional development that they were given.

Job satisfaction refers to the state of fulfillment, where faculty members feel motivated which influence their teaching performance. It is measured in terms of administrative support, compensation, and interpersonal relation, and their perspective toward their job.

Table 2: The Level of Job Satisfaction among Faculty Members on Administrative Support

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Qualitative Interpretation
1. My institution allows opportunities for professional/staff development.	3.40	0.67	Agree	Satisfied
2. Administrators seem willing to make changes as necessary for school improvement.	3.48	0.57	Agree	Satisfied
3. Administrators are supportive of teachers pursuing higher degrees.	3.42	0.65	Agree	Satisfied
4. Administrators have confidence in my professional judgment of circular implementation.	3.23	0.62	Agree	Satisfied
5. Administrators are interested in my opinions.	3.17	0.62	Agree	Satisfied
6. There are opportunities for professional advancement at the school.	3.35	0.61	Agree	Satisfied
7. My school provides sufficient instructional resources, supplies, and equipment to meet the needs of the students.	3.18	0.60	Agree	Satisfied
8. The observation/evaluation methods fit my needs as an educator.	3.18	0.54	Agree	Satisfied
9. The administrators are effective leaders within the school.	3.30	0.59	Agree	Satisfied
Overall Mean	3.34	0.61	Agree	Satisfied
LEGEND:				
Range	Verbal Description	Qualitative Interpretation		
3.50-4.00	Strongly agree	Very satisfied		
2.50-3.49	Agree	Satisfied		
1.50-2.49	Disagree	Dissatisfied		
1.00-1.49	Strongly disagree	Very dissatisfied		

SAIT faculty members felt that administrators appear to be willing to make changes as needed for school development (3.48), and administrators are supportive of instructors pursuing further education (3.42), an institution allows opportunities for professional/staff development (3.40). It implies that the school as an organization adapts to organizational change to remain competitive and to meet the demands of time. Also, the school desires to provide opportunities for professional development because this ensures its personnel and staff to be competent in their

respective profession. Constructs that obtained the lowest mean scores were: the observation/evaluation methods fit my needs as an educator (3.18), and administrators are interested in my opinions (3.17) which tells that teachers' evaluation serves as substantial practiced improvement motivations. Therefore, the results of such assessments give teachers with useful feedback regarding their educational effectiveness, which they may utilize to build and enhance their performance.

Table 3: The Level of Job Satisfaction among Members on Compension

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Qualitative Interpretation
1. I am satisfied with my salary.	3.22	0.61	Agree	Satisfied
2. I am satisfied with my fringe benefits package.	3.17	0.56	Agree	Satisfied
3. I am satisfied with the amount of my company's pays toward my benefits.	3.20	0.58	Agree	Satisfied
4. I am satisfied with my yearly salary increase.	3.12	0.64	Agree	Satisfied
5. I am satisfied with my company's pay structure.	3.15	0.61	Agree	Satisfied
6. I am satisfied with the information my company gives about pay issues in my job.	3.20	0.58	Agree	Satisfied
7. I am satisfied with the consistency of my company's pay policy.	3.02	0.62	Agree	Satisfied
8. I am satisfied how my company administers pay.	3.18	0.60	Agree	Satisfied
Overall Mean	3.15	0.60	Agree	Satisfied
LEGEND:	Range	Verbal Description	Qualitative Interpretation	
	3.50-4.00	Strongly agree	Very satisfied	
	2.50-3.49	Agree	Satisfied	
	1.50-2.49	Disagree	Dissatisfied	
	1.00-1.49	Strongly disagree	Very dissatisfied	

In terms of compensation, the results revealed that the faculty members agreed (3.22) that they are satisfied with their existing salary. They are also satisfied with the amount of their company's pays toward their benefits (3.20), administration of pay (3.18), fringe benefits package (3.17), and pay structure (3.15). However, among the indicators, the consistency of their company's pay policy earned the lowest mean (3.02). The results imply that compensation is a

necessary tool for increasing organizational performance and sustained competitiveness as it serves as a critical component for employee relationship and single most significant operating cost for many organizations.

Thus, school administration has to structure personnel and compensation plans accordingly properly.

Table 4: The Level of Job Satisfaction among Faculty Member on Interpersonal Relation

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Qualitative Interpretation
1. There is trust and mutual respect within the school among teacher and administrator.	3.35	0.61	Agree	Satisfied
2. Decisions that affect the entire school are made collaboratively.	3.35	0.66	Agree	Satisfied
3. Expectations are communicated effectively.	3.20	0.61	Agree	Satisfied
4. Collaboration between teachers at school is encouraged.	3.37	0.52	Agree	Satisfied
5. The overall expectations of faculty members by the administrators are reasonable.	3.12	0.52	Agree	Satisfied
6. Teachers are empowered at my school.	3.20	0.55	Agree	Satisfied
7. Teachers have opportunity to play an active role in the decision-making process in the school.	3.20	0.58	Agree	Satisfied
8. Rules for students conduct are enforced by administrators in a consistent manner.	3.18	0.62	Agree	Satisfied
9. Overall, I am treated as a professional by my colleagues.	3.37	0.61	Agree	Satisfied
Overall Mean	3.26	0.59	Agree	Satisfied
LEGEND:	Range	Verbal Description	Qualitative Interpretation	
	3.50-4.00	Strongly agree	Very satisfied	
	2.50-3.49	Agree	Satisfied	
	1.50-2.49	Disagree	Dissatisfied	
	1.00-1.49	Strongly disagree	Very dissatisfied	

Additionally, in terms of interpersonal relationships it can be noted that among the constructs which obtained the highest mean scores are: collaboration between teachers at school is encouraged (3.37), I am treated as a professional by my colleagues (3.37), and there is trust and mutual respect within the school among teacher and administrator (3.35). It implies that individuals working together in the organization have a strong association like San Agustin Institute of Technology (SAIT). Teachers and administrators have a particular bond that allows them to perform to the best of their abilities which eventually radiates positive

ambiance at the workplace. However, constructs that earned the lowest mean scores are: rules for student’s conduct are enforced by administrators in a consistent manner (3.18), and the overall expectations of faculty members by the administrators are reasonable (3.12) which suggest that consistency is one of the more important keys to addressing students conduct that sets limits and gives effective consequences among the students. Additionally, rapport, empathy, and trust are manifested within the organization where administrators and teachers get along well for a positive and healthy environment at the workplace.

Table 5: The Extent of Perspective towards Jobs among Faculty Members on Organizational

INDICATORS	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Qualitative Interpretation
1. Our administrators have a closed monitor to all employees’ productivity.	3.27	0.52	Agree	Satisfied
2. Administrators establishes long-term strategies for our institution.	3.25	0.54	Agree	Satisfied
3. We have programs that encourage diversity of our workforce (in terms of age, gender or race).	3.23	0.62	Agree	Satisfied
4. Internal policies prevent discrimination in employee’s compensation and promotion.	3.18	0.57	Agree	Satisfied
5. Our institution seeks to comply with all laws regulating hiring and employee benefits.	3.32	0.57	Agree	Satisfied
6. Our institution has comprehensive code of conduct.	3.26	0.66	Agree	Satisfied
7. Administrators support employees who acquire additional education.	3.33	0.68	Agree	Satisfied
8. Flexible company policies enable employees to better coordinate work and personal life.	3.37	0.52	Agree	Satisfied
9. We have programs that encourage diversity of our workforce (in terms of age, gender or race)	3.37	0.52	Agree	Satisfied
10. Our institution encourages partnership with the local communities.	3.27	0.69	Agree	Satisfied
Overall Mean	3.28	0.59	Agree	Satisfied
LEGEND:	Range	Verbal Description	Qualitative Interpretation	
	3.50-4.00	Strongly agree	Very satisfied	
	2.50-3.49	Agree	Satisfied	
	1.50-2.49	Disagree	Dissatisfied	
	1.00-1.49	Strongly disagree	Very dissatisfied	

Perspective towards job is the ability of faculty members to evaluate his/her profession to perform better in teaching. It is measured by assessing the level of organizational and personal perspective among faculty members. The extent of perspective towards jobs among faculty members on organizational perspective shows that among the indicator that obtained the highest means are: Flexible company policies enable employees to better coordinate work and personal life (3.37), we have programs that encourage diversity of our workforce (in terms of age, gender or race) (3.37), and Administrators support employees who acquire additional education (3.33). As far as the flexibility of school policies, school promotes flexible policies that would make working a good business sense and bring the following improvements such as the chance to have extended working hours for beating the deadlines of pertinent documents to be submitted in Commission on Higher Education (CHED), Department of Education (DepEd), or TESDA.

Meanwhile, the indicator that earned the lowest mean score is, internal policies prevent discrimination in employee’s compensation and promotion (3.18) which is right in the case of San Agustin Institute of Technology because the school has a Personnel Performance Appraisal System (PPAS) which runs in a three-year cycle. PPAS is a systematic review of employee performance and understanding of a person’s skills for future growth and development. Company performance evaluation is referred to as investment that can be justified by following benefits: 1. Performance appraisal assists administrators in determining promotion strategies for effective personnel. In this instance, inefficient employees may be fired or demoted. 2. Performance appraisal aids in the selection of compensation packages for employees. Performance appraisal allows for merit rating. A performance’s worth is determined via performance appraisal. Performance-based compensation packages may include bonuses, high wage rates, extra benefits, allowances, and pre-requisites. Merit is essential standards rather than seniority (Management Study Guide, 2018).

Table 6: The Extent of Perspective towards Jobs among Faculty Members on Personal Perspective

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Qualitative Interpretation
1. I find real enjoyment in my job.	3.42	0.53	Agree	Satisfied
2. I am seldom bored with my job.	2.97	0.74	Agree	Satisfied
3. I like my job better than the average person.	3.42	0.50	Agree	Satisfied
4. I feel fairly well satisfied with my job.	3.27	0.66	Agree	Satisfied
5. I would be very happy to spend the rest of my career in this organization.	3.18	0.65	Agree	Satisfied
6. I feel like "part of the family" at my organization.	3.33	0.66	Agree	Satisfied
7. I feel "emotionally attached" to this organization.	3.27	0.58	Agree	Satisfied
8. This organization has a great deal of personal meaning of me.	3.30	0.56	Agree	Satisfied
9. I feel a strong sense of belonging to my organization.	3.20	0.68	Agree	Satisfied
Overall Mean	3.26	0.62	Agree	Satisfied
LEGEND:	Range	Verbal Description	Qualitative Interpretation	
	3.50-4.00	Strongly agree	Very satisfied	
	2.50-3.49	Agree	Satisfied	
	1.50-2.49	Disagree	Dissatisfied	
	1.00-1.49	Strongly disagree	Very dissatisfied	

Regarding with personal perspective, the results revealed that teachers earned better scores in the following indicators: finding real enjoyment in a job (3.42), I like my job better than the average person (3.42), and I feel like "part of the family" at my organization (3.33). There are many instances where teachers find real enjoyment in their work in school. It could be personal values, and the culture of the environment is essential elements to consider. In school, each one almost knows each other from primary education department up college department because of the population's calculability. Additionally, if the college department needs the expertise of a full-time employee in primary education, he/she can also do a part-time job because the school utilizes human resources and expertise. SAIT as a community observes a sense of familiarity. Anyone can exchange smile to one another while walking around the campus. The result shows that teachers enjoy their job. They felt more passionate and energized in teaching, because they seem happy at work and they love what they are doing, productivity is bolstered, and their

performance is enhanced. They are more likely to be positive, driven, to learn more quickly, to make fewer mistakes, and to make better business judgments. On other hand, indicators that earned the lowest mean scores are: I would be very happy to spend the rest of my career in this organization (3.18), and I am seldom bored with my job (2.97). Though the mean scores are low, it still implies that teachers hold to have a firm agreement with these behaviors implying that teachers create a positive feedback loop that fuels productivity and make them stay in the organization for a lifetime. Additionally, the teachers feel confident and secure with the work which drives them to enjoy work and overcome obstacles in the workplace as well. In order to maintain a high level of professional performance in these conditions, teachers must accept personal responsibility for their performance, growth, and development. According to Mohanty (2000) teacher performance in the field of education has an essential contribution. The greatest influential profession in society is teaching (Sarital and Tomer, 2004).

Table 7: Teachers’ Teaching Performance in term of Knowledge of Subject Matter, Personal and Social Trait, Teaching Skills and Classroom Management

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Qualitative Interpretation
A. Effectiveness of Teaching				
Knowledge of Subject Matter	4.25	0.337	Very Satisfactory	High Teaching Performance
Teaching Skills	4.28	0.297	Very Satisfactory	High Teaching Performance
Classroom Management	4.24	0.392	Very Satisfactory	High Teaching Performance
B. Personal and Social Trait	4.29	0.351	Very Satisfactory	High Teaching Performance
Overall Mean	4.26	0.344	Very Satisfactory	High Teaching Performance

LEGEND:

Range	Verbal Description	Qualitative Interpretation
1.00-1.49	Poor	Very Low Teaching Performance
1.50-2.49	Fair	Low Teaching Performance
2.50-3.49	Satisfactory	Moderate Teaching Performance
3.50-4.49	Very Satisfactory	High Teaching Performance
4.50-5.00	Excellent	Very High Teaching Performance

Teaching Performance pertains to active teaching ability of faculty members using the Teaching Performance Evaluation Instrument of San Agustin Institute of Technology. The result indicated that teachers earned a very satisfactory performance in all indicators. Personal and social trait (4.29) comes first in rank which includes dressing modestly and appropriately, confidence, rapport with students, sense of humor, and flexibility. Followed by teaching skills (4.28) which encompasses teachers’ communication, the relevance of the subject matter and its practicality, encouraging critical thinking among learners, integrating Christian values, and appropriateness of drills, seatwork, and assignments. As to the knowledge of subject

matter (4.25) which comes fourth in rank, this covers ample understanding of the subject matter taught, organization, and relevance of materials used. Finally, classroom management (4.24) which received the lowest rank undertakes commanding student respect, tactful discipline, fairness in dealing with students, and firmness and consistency. It means that teachers impact on student learning and may even make a difference in their lives. As a support to the findings, a teacher’s quality is an essential factor of academic performance; however, specific characteristics to be a good teacher (Hanushek & Rivkin, 2006). The extent and merit of education received by a teacher is a sensible place to begin when considering teacher quality.

Table 8: Correlations analysis of job satisfaction, perspective , demographic profile and teaching performance among faculty members

INDICATORS	CORRELATION COEFFICIENT	PROBABILITY
Job satisfaction	-0.047	0.722ns
Compensation	-0.199	0.128ns
Interpersonal relation	0.018	0.892ns
Administrative support	0.069	0.599ns
Perspective	0.025	0.851ns
Personal	0.107	0.417ns
Organizational	-0.046	0.727ns
Demographic Profile		
Age	0.108	0.409ns
Gender	0.054	0.681ns
Length of service	0.042	0.750ns
Educational qualification	0.137	0.297ns

ns not significant

Correlation analysis revealed no significant relationship existing in the relationship between work satisfaction ($r=-0.047$; $p=0.722$) along with its factor variables namely: compensation ($r=-0.199$; $p=0.128$); interpersonal relation ($r=0.018$; $p=0.892$); and administrative support ($r=0.069$; $p=0.599$). Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted, which states that there is no substantial relationship between faculty members' job satisfaction and teaching performance. It means that in the case of San Agustin Institute of Technology, teaching performance is not related to job satisfaction because teachers managed to perform satisfactorily despite their meager salary, interpersonal relation, and administrative support.

As to the extent of perspective towards the job, correlation analysis yielded no significant relationship on teaching performance as indicated ($r=0.025$; $p=0.851$). This is likewise true among its dimensions: personal $r=0.107$; $p=0.417$ and organizational ($r=0.046$; $p=0.727$). Hence, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between the extent of perspective towards their job, and teaching performance among faculty members is accepted. It implies that teaching performance, in some fashion, is not related to perspective towards the job. Teachers in school are more likely driven by other factors other than that of perspective towards the job. As opposed to other research findings, a review of salient organizational climate literature shows that individual-level perceptions about their work environment have significant effects on their work attitudes, motivation, and performance (Parker et al., 2003).

As to the demographic profile, no significant relationship resulted in age ($r=0.108$; $p=0.409$); gender ($r=0.054$; $p=0.681$); length of service ($r=0.042$; $p=0.750$); and educational qualification ($r=0.137$; $p=0.297$). It means teachers' performance is not related to their age, gender, length of service, and educational qualification. Teachers perform at their best because they have high regard for their profession regardless of their status. Because the school is relatively smaller compared to other private universities in the region, competition among fellow teachers is scarce. However, Jaime and Jamie (2004) discovered that demographic features of faculty members were only marginally connected to overall job satisfaction. Several studies imply that age (Clark, Oswald, & Warr, 1995), gender (Clark, 1997; Clark & Oswald, 1996; Sousa-Poza & Sousa Poza, 2000), and education (Clark & Oswald, 1996; Tsang, Rumberger, & Levin, 1991) are important factors in teacher job satisfaction.

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